

Implementation of Fathul Muin's Teaching Material Books to Improve Santri's Competence at Tanwirunnida' Mungkid Islamic Boarding School, Central Java

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ABSTRACT

Fathul Muin, a book of fiqh by Sheikh Zakariya al-Ansari al-Maliki. Fiqh teaching materials (Fathul Muin) consist of seven volumes which have several components, including: First: discussing issues of purity, prayer, fasting, zakat, pilgrimage and their laws. Second: Discuss the subject of buying and selling transactions and the law. Third: Marriage and its laws, finally war and its laws. Types of R&D research and data collection techniques using observation, interviews and documentation. The results of research on the educational material of the Book of Fathul Muin are very useful for students in understanding Ushul al-Fiqh and fiqh lessons, and the learning process becomes very interesting. The inhibiting factors are the lack of support from parents in carrying out the learning process and the diversity of students' abilities. Student competence is expected to be able to connect three aspects, namely cognitive aspects, psychomotor aspects and emotional aspects. This book is often used as the main teaching material in the study of Maliki jurisprudence and as a reference in solving everyday Islamic legal problems. Fathul Muin is an important reference in the study and understanding of Islamic law.

INTRODUCTION

The teaching process is the delivery of knowledge to students using formal and informal channels, while the learning process requires several components including Ustadz, students, subjects being taught or knowledge (Rusman, 2018).

Fathul Muin is a book by Sheikh Zakariya Al-Ansari Al-Maliki. This book is one of the most famous books of Maliki jurisprudence in the Islamic world. Fathul Muin is a major work that discusses various issues of Islamic law in the Maliki school of thought in simple, clear and easy-to-understand language.

This book consists of seven volumes covering different and important topics in Maliki fiqh, such as worship, transactions, marriage, inheritance, etc. Each chapter of this book has been systematically arranged and fully explained, making it a useful guide for scholars, scholars and anyone who wants to study Maliki jurisprudence.

Fathul Muin is also known for its comprehensive and complete contents of Islamic law. This book has been widely studied in various Islamic educational institutions as the main educational material in the study of Maliki jurisprudence. In addition, this book is often used as a reference in solving problems of Islamic law in everyday life.

One of Fath Moin's strengths is that the language used in this book is easily understood by the general public. The explanation given is not too technical so that it makes it easier for the reader to understand the contents of the book. This book also contains a clear reference system, so that readers can explore the basics of Islamic law described in the book.

In general, the Book of Fathul Muin is considered one of the most important and influential books of Maliki jurisprudence in the Islamic world. With easy-to-understand language and complete explanations, this book is a reference for many people in studying and understanding Islamic law.

THEORETICAL REVIEWS

The curriculum occupies a central place in education because the curriculum is able to direct all activities to achieve educational goals (Chamisijatin & Permana, 2020; Hikmawati & Hosnan, 2022). Azra's approach occupies a major place in education, because it is about determining the direction, content and process of education which ultimately determines the type and qualifications of graduates of an educational institution (Azra, 2018). In other languages, the curriculum is the main guideline for formal education, because the curriculum is an embodiment of the educational goals to be achieved (Arifin, 2020; Rusman, 2018).

Based on the reasons mentioned above, the researcher tried to develop the Tanwirunnida' Mungkid Islamic Boarding School in Central Java, Central Java by making educational materials by compiling theories or principles of fiqh (Kitab Fathul Muin) in a systematic, easy to understand and fun way, fiqh . The teaching material (Fath Al-Ma'in) has several components, including: First: Discusses issues of chastity, prayer, fasting, zakat, pilgrimage and its laws.

Second: Discussing the subject matter of buying and selling transactions and the law. Third: Marriage and its laws, finally war and its laws. Al-Millibari (2018: 03).

A literature study on the Book of Fathul Muin, and it is possible to benefit from the following references: 1). Al-Baghdadi and Muhammad Al-Tanbih and the most respected of the nation's Islamic legislators. Beirut: Dar Al-Qalam, 1999. This book discusses the books of Islamic law and provides an explanation of Fathul Muin as one of the important books in the field of fiqh. 2). Salah al-Din and Hassan Fathul Muin in a short publication interpretation. Lebanon: Dar Al-Ilm for Millions, 2003. This book is a study of the book Fath Al-Maen, focusing on aspects of interpretation and explanation of the arguments contained in the book. Shebib, TI (2022) 3). Al-Quraini, Fathul Muin and Al-Fakira with the characteristics of their teachings merge. Riyadh: Dar Al-Minhaj, 2010. This book describes the characteristics and legal principles of the Maliki school of thought contained in the book Fath Al-Mu'in. 4). Abushouq, AI 'Mahlan's Gifted Libraries: Islamic Libraries of the Twentieth Century.' Journal of Islamic Studies, Vol. 21, no. 3, 2010, p. 339-356. This article discusses the collection of books at the Mahlan Library in Cairo, including Fath Moin's book. Rosedin, DN (2022). 5). Orihuela, J. 'Islamization of the Acehnese in the Seventeenth and Eighteenth Century: An Evaluation.' Islamic Studies, Vol. 23, no. 2, 2016, p. 215 - 256. This article comments on the influence of the book Fath Moin on the spread of the Maliki school of thought in Aceh, Indonesia. Azra, A.; (2016).

In conducting a literature review of the Book of Fathul Muin, it is important to find sources that provide in-depth and authoritative explanations about the book. In addition, it is also necessary to consider the author's point of view and approach in providing an analysis of the book.

Studying the theory of essays in the Book of Fathul Muin, several theoretical approaches can be used as follows:

1). Historical Approach: By using this approach, the article can explain the origins of the Fathul Muin Book, its author, its historical context, its influence and its important role in the development of Islamic jurisprudence. That is, the article will discuss the history of the book and the importance of this work in the world of Islamic scholars. 2). Literary Approach: This approach focuses on the analysis of the structure, writing style, and language used in the Fathul Muin Book. Essays can examine how the author uses certain language and writing styles to convey the fiqh concepts in the book. 3). Philosophical approach: This approach involves analyzing the fiqh concepts contained in the book Fath al-Mu'in. Articles can analyze the arguments and theoretical basis used in the book, as well as provide an understanding of the philosophical ideas that underlie the writing of the book. 4). Social Approach: This approach discusses the social impact of the book Fath Al Moein on Islamic society. Entries can discuss how this book influences the daily life practices of Muslims, the relationship between Muslims and Islamic law, and how society responds to this book. 5). Comparative Approach: This approach compares the Book of Fathul Muin with other fiqh books or with different fiqh approaches. These

articles can identify the similarities and differences between this book and other books in terms of the method of writing, the legal sources used, and the uniqueness of the approach in the Book of Fathul Muin.

When conducting a theoretical study of the Book of Fathul Muin, it is important to choose a theoretical approach that fits the purpose of the article and can provide an in-depth understanding of the contents and context of the book.

METHODOLOGY

Researchers in this study decided to use research and development methods that fall into the category of combined research methods. Actually, there are several terms in the discussion of this developmental research. Ritchie and Kellen use the name R&D (research and design development). Thiagarajan uses a 4D model which stands for Define, Design, Develop and Publish. Has and promotes the use of the term ADDIE (Analysis, Design Development, Implementation Evaluation). Meanwhile, Borg and Gall are two figures who use the name R&D, which means Sugiono Development Research, (2015:28)

This understanding is different from the opinion of Nusa Putra (2011: 67) which says that research and development is defined as a method of deliberate and systematic research that aims to formulate, improve, develop, produce and test the effectiveness of certain superior, effective products. , efficient, productive and meaningful. The main studies in this study are observation (observation), interviews and documentation. Research and development (R&D) is a process or method used to validate and develop products. Hamzah, (2019: 45) R&D steps are potential problems, gathering product design information, design validation, design improvement, product trials, product reviews, and trial use. While the development procedure is a preliminary study and typical development planning.

The research methodology or methodological approach that can be used in a certain book, Fath, is as follows: 1). Historical Approach: This method involves tracing and gathering information about the origins of a particular book of Fath, its author, and the historical context in which it was written. For this reason, primary sources such as classic books and author biographies can be used as references. Secondary sources such as historical records, articles and previous research can also be used to gain a more complete understanding of the book. 2). Text Analysis Method: This method involves a detailed analysis of the contents of the Fathul Muin Book. Articles can investigate the legal arguments and concepts described in this book, and identify the opinions and arguments used by the author. This technique involves quoting and interpreting the text of the book accurately and critically. 3). Comparative approach: This method includes comparing the book of Fathul Muin with other fiqh books. Articles may compare the methods, legal opinions, or literary approaches used in this book with similar books. This technique makes it possible to assess the contribution and uniqueness of the Book of Fathul Muin in the context of Islamic fiqh literature. 4). Qualitative Approach: This method involves in-depth investigation of the viewpoints, opinions and interpretations

given in the Kitab Fathul Muin. Articles can interview fiqh experts or scholars who study this book, or carry out qualitative data analysis such as the opinions of other scholars on this book. 5). Social Approach: This method involves researching the social impact of the book Fath Al-Maeen on the Islamic community. Articles may include interviews, notes or analysis of documents to understand how this book is used in the daily life of Muslims or in legal decision-making.

The choice of research method depends on the purpose and focus of the article and the available sources. A combination of methods can also be used to gain a comprehensive understanding of a particular opening book.

RESULTS

Research results in a particular book of Fath Search can cover the following aspects: 1. Analysis of the contents of the book: Search can include an in-depth analysis of the contents of a particular book of Fath, identification and explanation. It discusses topics and issues of legitimacy and various Islamic concepts. This can reveal the contribution of the Book of Fathul Muin in enriching the understanding of Islamic jurisprudence and law. 2. Evaluating the methodology and approach: This research was able to examine the approach and methodology used by the author of the Book of Fathul Muin in building propositions and compiling Islamic law. This can include assessing the correctness and accuracy of the approaches used, and their impact on the final output of the book. 3. Analysis of the arguments used: Articles can include an analysis of the arguments used in the Book of Fathul Muin. This can include exploring and discussing the arguments used by the author, as well as evaluating the strength and accuracy of the arguments cited. 4. Relevance of the Book of Fathul Muin to the social and time context: This research can analyze the significance of the Book of Fathul Muin in the current social context and time. This could include exploring whether the laws in the book are still relevant to the state and the development of modern society. 5. Scholars' and scholars' responses to books: Research can be in the form of exploring responses, criticisms, or recognition by scholars and scholars of certain conquered books. This can provide further understanding of the acceptance and influence of the book among the clergy and the Muslim community. 6. Influence and Influence of the Book of Fathul Muin: This research can examine the impact and influence of the book of Fathul Muin on the understanding of Islamic law and the lives of Muslims. This could include exploring the use of books in making legal decisions, their application to religious practice, and their role in shaping Islamic thought and belief.

The results of research on the Book of Fathul Muin can provide insight into the content, methodology, relevance and influence of the book in scientific, social and religious contexts.

Research Findings Results

General Findings In this case, the researcher will present some general research results which will be used as a reference or initial study in the development of Fath Al-Moeen teaching materials at the Tanwirunnida' Mungkid Islamic Boarding School, Central Java, Manjkid, Central Java, as follows:

History of its Establishment

In this section, the researcher describes the findings of special research on the application of special Fatah educational materials to increase the competence of students at the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School, Mungkid, Central Java, Mungkid, Central Java and the supporting and inhibiting factors for implementing the special Fatah. Teaching materials to improve the competence of Tanurunida Mungkid Islamic Boarding School students in Central Java according to the research focus.

Implementation of Fathul Muin's educational materials to improve the competence of students at the Tanwerunida Mungkid Islamic Boarding School, Central Java. During the research the researchers looked at the educational interactions that took place at the Tanwirunnida' Mungkid Islamic Boarding School, Central Java, where there were educational materials used in educational books such as Fath Moin and other books in understanding and reading them.

Vision, Mission and Objectives of Pondok Pesantren Tanwirunnida' 1) Organizing Islamic boarding schools by upholding and developing Islamic values rohmatal lilalamin by upholding Pancasila values, the 1945 Constitution, the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, Bhineka Tunggal Ika, justice, tolerance , humanity, sincerity, togetherness, and other noble values, in order to achieve the general goals of Islamic boarding schools that are in line with the vision, mission and goals of national development; and 2) Strive for and maintain the fulfillment of the elements of Islamic boarding schools (arkanul ma'had) and the spirit or characteristics of Islamic boarding schools (ruhul ma'had) as applicable provisions.

The structure of the Ustadzsan of the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School

Secretariat: Rambeanak2 Hamlet, Rambeanak Village, Mungkid District, Magelang Regency.

Gambar 1. Struktur Kepengurusan Pondok Pesantren Tanwirunnida'

Teaching materials in the designated opening

According to Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrofik Fathul Muin's educational materials explained In an interview on 22 July 2023, explained the following:

"The educational material in Fathul Muin is very difficult educational material both from the text editor and from the language used. Because it was written before the 20th century, at that time the pious scholar Zakariya al-Anshuri was famous for his language which was difficult and required deep reflection to understand. The educational material in Fathul Muin is of high quality and its implementation still requires a long and rigorous process. Apart from that, there must also be an Ustadz who always guides the students to understand it."

Based on the results of observations and interviews conducted by researchers, it can be concluded that the educational material in Fathul Muin is high quality educational material and is included in the main subjects or considered in class promotion and graduation in elementary schools. Tanwirunnida' Islamic Boarding School, in the learning process At Tanwirunnida' Mungkid Islamic Boarding School, Central Java has several classifications or levels of education including the curriculum which is divided into three parts (components), first, the basic curriculum or (basic) is a

curriculum that includes the basics. subjects such as nahwu, shorrof and memorization. Second, the main curriculum or (Ushuliyah) is a curriculum that includes basic subjects such as Usul al-Fiqh, Jurisprudence, Meditation, History, Tajweed, Sufism and Hadith. The third is a supportive or (integrative) curriculum, which includes supporting materials such as religious lectures, memorizing grammar and honors, practicing prayers, practicing meditation, praying, shrouds and burial of bodies, sports, arrow training, recitation of mourning and rotipul. read zanji.

Figure 2: Source of Fathul Muin, Popular Fiqh Book of Santri at Islamic Boarding Schools – LP Maarif NU Central Java

Learning methods

The learning method that is often used is the lecture method. That is, this method is applied by lecturing or conveying information orally to students. This method is the most practical and economical way, and does not require a lot of tools.

As stated by St. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. explain:

'The teaching method with lectures aims to make teaching materials eye-opening not only to improve the quality of students and to encourage an easy and enjoyable learning process for both Ustadz and students. the ability of the students and the ability of the Ustadz Council to master subjects effectively. Because few students still don't understand the material you convey as high as the others. But his method is less effective.'

This is what Helmi also felt when he said:

"The learning method used in the application of Fath Al-Mu'min's educational materials is a lecture that focuses on only one direction, namely from Ustadz to students, causing a lack of understanding of the lesson and causing sleepiness in class."

Based on the results of the observations and interviews above, the researcher can conclude that the learning method applied by Pondok Pesantren Tanwirunnida' uses the lecture method which focuses on only one Ustadz. However, in the process of implementing this method, it has many advantages, including: Ustadz can easily and freely monitor and control the situation or learning conditions of students in class. However, this method has weaknesses, namely students get bored faster, sleepy, and students do not understand.

Learning curriculum

When viewed from the time allocation and learning methods, the application of open-ended educational materials is something that is taken into account because it is related to the implementation of teaching and learning activities, Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. explained: In an interview on 12 July 2023 that:

Starting from 2000, the study time for the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School was still integrated with public schools, namely from 07.30 to 13.30 WIB. The Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School began to have its own class For public schools, for daiya activities in the morning from 7.30 to 0.11.00 WIB, but this has changed again in 2020, especially Islamic education in the afternoon from 12.30 to 0.16 00 WIB Because of its great influence regarding the application of Fathul Muin to teaching materials and learning methods that are still classic, namely the use of the lecture method has many weaknesses and not only that, but also interpreted by students and read by their Ustadz against the yellow text of the book.

Based on the results of the observations and interviews above, the researcher can conclude that the curriculum implemented by Pondok Pesantren Tanwirunnida' starting in 2000 is still below the ceiling of public schools, namely from 07.30 to 13.30 WIB. However, along with developments and changing times, study time at the Tannerunida Islamic Boarding School has begun to be separated from public schools, for one day's activities in the morning from 07.30 to 0.11.00 WIB. However, it has changed again in 2020 so far, namely Islamic religious education in the afternoon from 12.30 to 0.16 00 WIB. Because it is very influential on the application of educational materials in Fath Al-Mu'in, as well as learning methods that are still traditional, namely the use of the lecture method which has many weaknesses and not only that, but also students interpret it and their Ustadz read it against it. Yellow book text.

Learning assessment

In terms of assessing teaching materials for a 'certain conquest', the santri or santri find it very difficult, as was experienced by Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. explained: In an interview on 12 July 2023 that:

'The educational material at Fathul Muin is still far from the current curriculum because it is caused by several factors, namely delays in mastering Arabic grammar, students' interest in learning is very weak, the material provided is not interesting, and learning is just one way to cause boredom. '

Meanwhile, according to Helmy, an evaluation of the application of Fatah's special education materials in an interview on 12 July 2023 explained as follows:

'The background to the application of Fathul Muin's educational materials at the Tanweerida Islamic Boarding School is that there are many students who only know law without any argument. Many students complained that they did not understand the material presented by the Ustadzn. With regard to this subject. The educational background of the santri in the past was that some graduated from elementary school, masters and masters. The Ustadz Council lacks mastery of the subject matter and devotes little time to it.'

In line with that, the students also voiced Hilmi Fateh al-Maeen's teaching material, as he conveyed in an interview on 12 July 2023, stating that:

'Difficulties in understanding certain opening lessons are due to inadequate mastery of grammar and adverbs, the language used by the Ustadz is not easy to understand, little study time especially during the day, many students are sleepy and the material is boring. .'

According to Helmy, the difficulties faced by the Book of Fathul Muin in educational materials are as follows:

'Difficulties in understanding the study of the Fathul Muin Book are due to inadequate mastery of grammar and adverbs, language that is difficult to digest and learning times that are not fun or boring.'

Based on the results of observations and interviews conducted by researchers regarding the evaluation of Fathul Muin's learning at the Tanurunida Islamic Boarding School, it consists of three components, namely first, the academic abilities of Ustadz or Ustadz. , because in the learning process Ustadz has a very big role in implementing the learning process, apart from that Ustadz are also required to use various types of learning methods to provide understanding to students. Second, the dayah curriculum, the curriculum has a very large influence, because it is a benchmark for the success of an educational institution starting from SK, KD, methods, time allocation and material taught and closing. Third, the background ability of the students, because the differences in the background of the students have an impact on the understanding of the material taught by the Ustadz, so that the Ustadz must have various skills, both in how to deliver the material. or behavior towards students, and patience and persistence in guiding students.

This assessment connects three aspects, namely cognitive aspects, emotional aspects, and psychomotor aspects, so that only one aspect is prioritized in the assessment of the three disciplines. Instead, attention should be paid to other aspects that must be considered when promoting and graduating from the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School'.

Absorption capacity of students

Meanwhile, students' understanding of educational material in Fathul Muin is very important in the learning process of the material being taught. Because this is the benchmark for the company's success, as revealed by Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. explained: In an interview on 12 July 2023 that:

The absorption capacity of Tannurunida Islamic Boarding School students for Fathul Muin's teaching materials is still lacking and can be said to be lower than the standard Islamic curriculum in general, both in terms of understanding and reading Arabic. According to my observations, this will be resolved if all the Ustadzs of the Tanwarunida Islamic Boarding School conduct a needs analysis and analyze the capabilities of the santri or santri.'

This is in line with what was expressed by H. Daldiri as the Head of Men's Tanurunida Islamic Boarding School Development in an interview on 12 July 2023 explaining that:

'Absorption of educational material by students at the Mungkid Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School in Central Java at Fathul Muin will be normal if school education runs normally in terms of material absorption and management after operating between 4 to 10 years.'

As for the obstacles to implementing educational materials at Fath Al-Ma'in, the implementation process faces several obstacles, as revealed by the University of Applied Sciences. Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. explained: In an interview on 12 July 2023 that:

Obstacles in the process of applying Fateh Al-Ma'een's teaching materials at the Tannerunida Islamic Boarding School include: the different backgrounds of the students and their special abilities, many students or students do not know and understand Arabic grammar, and the large number of students or students prefer to play rather than study and managing the interior of the Undirected Tannerunida Islamic Boarding School.

In another part, what makes it difficult for students to understand a topic is, as explained by Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. said: In an interview on 12 July 2023, that:

Some of the reasons students find it difficult to understand subjects, namely because their parents (mother and father) are so busy that the burden of family life cannot be carried properly are abandoned children, namely children who live 'wild' or are free in society because other people their parents are busy with farmland. Economically, they come from poor or orphaned families and a strong desire from their parents to appear to be religiously intelligent and to be able to pray for them.

While Helmy said among the students:

"The reason why students find it difficult to understand subjects is because they are busy with other activities or because there are so many activities that we don't focus on studying them and learning becomes boring."

Based on the results of the observations and interviews above, the students' understanding of fiqh and ushul lessons is very low, as expressed by Sauma Rizqi and his friends, 'Fiqh and fiqh lessons are very difficult because they lack clarity. in the sense and the language used is not easy for us to understand, and we are also often sick and many are away.'

Benefits of teaching materials

According to the students, the benefits of Fathul Muin's teaching materials are as follows: '*Fathul Muin's teaching materials are very useful in understanding fiqh and fiqh science. Whereas from the beginning we were too confused to understand this lesson.*'

This is also in line with what was expressed by Hilya and other students who said: Maeen Fatah's teaching materials really help us understand the lessons. From the beginning we found it very difficult to understand the lessons of Usul al-Fiqh and fiqh, but it became easy for us and we feel the availability of educational materials at Fathul Muin helped us.

Based on the results of the interviews above, the researcher can conclude that Fathul Muin's teaching materials really help students understand their lessons and are easy to understand. With educational material, students feel happy and can learn independently. This educational material also provides new understanding for both students and Ustadz or tutors in carrying out the learning process and is easy to use as material for discussion to deepen the lessons of jurisprudence and jurisprudence.

Factors that support and hinder the application of Fath Al-Maeen teaching materials to improve the competence of the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School students'.

There are two supporting factors for the application of Fathul Muin's teaching materials at the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School at the global level, and those are supporting factors for the application of Fath Al-Ma'in's teaching materials.

1) internal factors

Internal factors in the application of educational materials First Fathul Muin, Ustadz with adequate academic abilities and students. Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. explained: In an interview on 12 July 2023 that:

'Implementation of special Fatah teaching materials at the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School' is mostly supported by several components. Internal factors,

the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School has caregivers who are qualified in the field of religion and caring for students, because among these caregivers there are graduates of the Islamic boarding school while the teaching staff have very high scientific quality because the teaching staff are very helpful in smooth running. Santri activities, both in physical and non-physical forms. Apart from that, the subjects taught have been arranged systematically, from the beginning students entered the pesantren until they graduated.'

Based on the results of the observations and interviews above, the researcher can conclude that the internal factors that support the learning of Usul al-Fiqh and Fiqh are teaching staff who have academic quality and are very knowledgeable in their field of specialization, especially those related to Usul. al-Fiqh. and jurisprudence studies.

2) external factors.

For external factors, we have worked with various stakeholders to assist various needs and activities at Islamic boarding schools, for example the local government or city government helping with financial problems, various types of training and counseling, etc.

The same thing was also expressed by St. Moh. Chalhlin explained in an interview dated 12 July 2023:

'Among the external factors is the condition of the students who are still very innocent and completely surrendered to their parents, especially those who enter Islamic boarding schools at the age of 15. This really supports us in the initial process of instilling moral values. as their initial basis. Students are registered here. '.

Based on observations and interviews conducted by researchers, in the implementation of teaching materials, Fathul Muin's teaching materials have two supporting factors, namely internal factors which include first, the lecturer's academic abilities. Educational motivator , manager, of course, knowledgeable.

Likewise, the teaching staff at the Tanurunida Islamic Boarding School have the academic ability to study the yellow book and speak Indonesian properly and correctly. Because most of the educators were graduates of Islamic boarding schools, respectively Sarang, Tomburo, Samalagan, Mahd Ali, his predecessor Siyafih Sokurijo Situbondo, Lerbyo and others. They have been struggling with the pesantren world for a long time, generally there are 12 and so on. Second, the learning resources are affordable. Availability of learning resources that are easily accessible to students in the learning process. Third, language that is communicative and easy to understand. Easy or no learning resources for students to use.

While external factors include cooperation with religious institutions in Bener Meriah, such as collaboration with Islamic boarding schools, MPU and

MPD in the affairs of Islamic boarding schools in Bener Meriah. In addition, the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School has a nanny who acts as a caregiver from Panji Marya, who has made an extraordinary contribution to the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School, both in development and in education.

Factors that hinder the application of open teaching materials are designated

As for the factors inhibiting the application of 'Fathul Muin' in educational materials, as stated by the Ustadz. Moh. Chalhin explained in an interview dated 12 July 2023:

'There are several obstacles in the implementation of Fateh Al Moeen's educational materials at the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School', including students, such as the circumstances of their departure from different regions and different intelligence abilities that make it difficult for leaders to provide understanding and material during the teaching and learning process, in addition to different behaviors. it has become a habit as long as they are still in their respective areas, it becomes an obstacle in guiding them to comply with the rules that have been set. the interests of other areas that are assigned and functioned according to their duties and functions, so that the role of learning becomes difficult.

On the other hand, in a conversation with Ust. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. explained: In an interview on 12 July 2023 that:

'In addition to technological developments, the influence on the behavior of students is one of the limitations in the application of educational materials for students. On the one hand, we have provided a lot of understanding or material about the virtues of educational material, but on the other hand, when they go home or on holidays, they use their free time to sit in coffee shops, play games or do other things, because our institution is located surrounded by several shops that provide food services. So there are students whose language and daily behavior. not according to what we teach them.'

The same thing was also expressed by St. Moh. Zae Nurrafik S.Pd. explained: In an interview on 12 July 2023 that:

'Obstacles in applying Fathul Muin's educational materials to students generally come from the students themselves. With different family backgrounds and environments, these are the main obstacles we face in changing their behavior and mentality. There are children with strong personalities and there are children with weak intelligence. The situation for students like this is exacerbated by environmental conditions during the day that provide food stall facilities. So we have to be more in caring for and guiding them.'

Based on observations and interviews conducted by researchers, in the implementation of educational materials, Fathul Muin's educational materials had two inhibiting factors, which were internal factors, namely: the limited intelligence of the students in understanding the subject matter. teaching and

learning process, and its difficulties. Standardizing the behavior of students due to regional differences and family backgrounds, as well as the lack of interest from other regions in carrying out the assigned tasks.

While external factors include the background of the students, the diversity of the abilities of the students, the learning environment, and the lack of support from parents

Based on the above data presentation in the process of applying these teaching materials to students at the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School, the conclusion from the research results is that the process of applying teaching materials at Fathul Muin has a very big influence. occupies an important place in the educational curriculum of the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School, but is limited by the background and abilities of the students who are still very low, such as:

1. Many students do not understand Arabic grammar so they have difficulty learning the book Fath Al-Ma'in, so the Ustadz has to repeat it several times.

2. Awareness of Islamic law has not been formed and it is not a burden for students when they do not understand what is explained by the Ustadz.
3. There needs to be teaching materials that help them understand the subjects being taught. Attractive design, easy to understand language, fun colors. Thus forming the desire and pleasure to learn the material.
4. Fathul Muin's teaching materials should be given more time to study them both arrogantly and for discussion.

To cultivate a love of matter. Santry's religious understanding of a case of fiqh law and its arguments is still lacking for several reasons, including

Not mastering classic books, very low enthusiasm for learning, and lack of motivation to study. In addition, the obstacle in understanding religious issues is the lack of support from the family. On the other hand, there are also supporting factors from the first teaching material at Fathul Muin, namely the academic abilities of the Ustadz. Ustadz have several positions in the learning process, namely mentors. Not only that, learning resources must be accessible to students and practical to use. Third, the language is communicative and easy to understand. Easy or no learning resources for students to use. That is, learning resources require special preparation, skills, and other supporting tools that can be used by students to learn.

External factors include cooperation with religious institutions in Bener Meriah, such as collaboration with Islamic boarding schools, MPU and MPD in the affairs of Islamic boarding schools in Bener Meriah. In addition, the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School has caregivers who have made an extraordinary contribution to the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School in development and education.

Meanwhile, there are two factors that hinder the application of Fathul Muin's educational materials throughout the world, namely:

(1) Background of the students. The economic background of the santri family greatly determines the learning process. Therefore it also affects whether or not it is easy to get educational media, because Islamic boarding schools especially provide convenience for students who are less fortunate. (2) Diversity of students' abilities. In the learning process, the learning environment has a great influence on students in improving their educational competence. Because by creating a conducive and enjoyable learning environment, the achievements of these students will increase.

However, what happened at the Tanwirunnida Islamic Boarding School was different. The learning environment has not been optimally formed with many conditions including frequent rainy seasons, students tend to play and lack interest in reading or writing and repeating the material.

Lack of parental support. While external factors are often expressed by the head of the school, namely Ust. Moh. Shlihah said:

'Most parents do not support their children's education, such as the motive of some parents to send their children to the Tannerunida Islamic Boarding School' so as not to disturb their parents. , and it is difficult for parents to comply with applicable regulations. While the competence of students to be achieved is to connect three aspects, namely perception, emotion and psychomotor.

DISCUSSION

When discussing articles in the book of Fathul Muin, several issues can be discussed as follows:

1. Contents of certain opening books: Articles can discuss in detail the contents of certain opening books. This includes the chapters or topics discussed in the book, the explanations of Islamic law contained therein, as well as the arguments and arguments used to support each discussion. 2. Legal approach in the book: Articles can review the legal approach used in Fathul Muin's book. This includes the ijihad methodology used by the author, the argumentative approach, as well as the methodology for compiling Islamic law. 3. Contribution of the book of Fathul Muin: The discussion may include the contribution of the book of Fathul Muin in the field of science or jurisprudence. This includes an explanation of how the book can provide an in-depth understanding of Islamic law, solve complex fiqh problems, or provide practical guidance in the daily lives of Muslims. 4. Comparison with other books: Articles can compare the Fathul Muin Book with other similar books or which discuss similar topics. It can summarize the similarities and differences in approach, content or legal solution offered by a particular opening book. 5. Impact on society: The discussion may include the impact of Fathul Muin's book on society or the Muslim community.

This could include how this book can be used by Islamic scholars or scholars in making legal decisions or providing religious advice to the public. 6. Relevance of the current book of Fatah: Articles can discuss the importance of the book Fathul Muin in the context of the life of Muslims today. Including the consideration of whether this book can still be used as a guide in dealing with new problems that arise in modern society. 7. Criticism and Evaluation: The discussion of the article may include a critical analysis of a particular book of Fath, from a scientific point of view and from a social context. Including covering the advantages and disadvantages of this book and the response of scholars or scholars to it.

The discussion of the article on The Book of Fathul Muin should be carried out in a comprehensive manner, providing accurate and in-depth information about the content, methodology and influence of this book on the lives of Muslims. In the tradition of Islamic boarding schools, especially Islamic boarding schools of the Salaf, there is a sequence of books that students need to study in various orders of Shari'a sciences. For example, the science of nahwu, there are basic books, namely the book of *ofjurniyah*, then *imrithi* to *alfiyah*. In this article, we will discuss the book *fathul mu'in*. Where this book usually becomes the number two order of books for students who want to study the classic book of the Shafi'i priest school. The order of the books is more or less like this: *fathul muin*, *fathul muin* and *fathul wahab*. The three standard books just now are very popular in many Islamic boarding schools. *Fathul muin* itself is a classic book of fiqh by Sheikh Zainuddin bin Abdul Aziz al-Malibari. Al-Malibari itself is the name of an area in India. This book is a *syarah* book (commentary) from the book *qurrotul 'ain*.

In terms of writing, the book of *fathul mu'in* has its own uniqueness compared to other fiqh books. From the initial discussion alone, Sheikh Zainuddin wrote the prayer chapter first. This is very different from fiqh books in general, which usually discuss the rules of purification (*thaharah*) in the first chapters. Besides that, the book of *fathul muin* is also known as a book that is quite difficult in placing the reference of a *dhomir* (pronoun). In discussing the conditions of prayer for example. If we examine the fiqh books in general, the conditions for prayer have certain chapters or *fasl* and the discussion doesn't go anywhere.

But this is very different in the book *fathul muin*. On page four of the book *Fathul Mu'in*, we are presented with a discussion of the meaning of the first terms and conditions that must be met before praying. What makes this book different is that the final discussion of the conditions for prayer ends on page 15. Even though at first glance there are only five conditions for prayer, namely facing the Qibla; clean the body, clothing and unclean places, clean from small and large hadats, entering prayer times and covering the genitals. But when explaining one by one, still dropping by to other discussions. For example, the requirement for prayer must be holy from small hadats, of course this discussion is still related to the chapter on ablution', so in that chapter the

discussion also describes ablution and its details. Such as procedures, traditions, things that cancel to cases that are interesting and important topics from the ablution chapter itself.

No wonder, if this book is not systematic. For scholars and connoisseurs of fiqh, there are challenges in studying line by line from the book of fathul muin. We are invited to think and reflect on the treasures of Islamic scholarship, the legacy of the Salafunas Sholihin scholars, which are different from most books. In addition, there are several "signs", a kind of discussion terminal in the book fathul muin. The terminal for this discussion will usually be bolded in the writing in the book. This discussion terminal is like a bus/public transportation terminal in cities, a place to stop, start and stop (sign, red) that needs to be underlined.

There is a discussion terminal called far'un. Far'un's simple language is a branch problem. So when we discuss unclean chapters, for example, Sheikh Zainuddin will discuss certain cases that are common in society in general. He explained it in detail. In addition, there are also those named tanbihun (warning) and faidah (benefits). So, in this terminal tanbihun, the author of the book seems to warn that the discussion under discussion contains a very important note. For example, the discussion about the permissibility of not praying in congregation.

Now, when there is tanbihun, mushonnif then explains the importance of explaining the legal statement of excuses for not carrying out congregational prayers because there are scholars who punish congregational prayers as fardhu ain, so it is necessary to explain excuses for the permissibility of not praying in congregation and he is not guilty if there is an excuse that has been explained .

In addition, there is also the term qoidah. Syekh Zainuddin in his work inserts the application of fiqh rules so that it makes it easier for us to learn fiqh. As the rule on page 13 reads:

أَنَّ مَا أَصْلُهُ الطَّهَارَةُ وَغَلَبَ الظَّنُّ تَنَجُّسُهُ لِنَجَاسَةِ النَّجَاسَةِ فِي مِثْلِهِ قَوْلَانِ مَعْرُوفَانِ يَقُولِي الْأَصْلُ وَالطَّاهِرُ أَوْ الْغَالِبُ أَرْجَحُهُمَا أَنَّهُ طَاهِرٌ

Meaning: actually the origin of something is if it is holy and most likely then there is something that pollutes it, then there are two famous qoul: following the law of origin (sacred) and its impure law (unclean). The most superior of the two opinions is sacred.

The text of the book above is an implementation of the fiqh rules:

الأصل بقاء ما كان على ما كان

Meaning: the law of origin is the persistence of something over the previous state.

So, when we find cases of doubt like the case in the Fathul Muin book earlier, we can simply argue with these fiqh rules.

Lastly, is *tatimmah* or *muhimmah* (completer/important). So one of Sheikh Zainuddin's habits is that before ending the discussion there is a *tatimmah* or *muhimmah* terminal as a completion of the *fasl*. When the *santri* want to easily learn this book of *fathul muin*, the *santri* usually use the book of *ianah ath-tolibin* as a *hasiyah* or marginal notes from the book of *fathul muin*. As its name means helper for students, this book of *i'alah ath-thalibin* is very helpful for students to learn the book of *fathul muin* which is quite complicated and different from most other books of *fiqh*. There is even an anecdote or advice from the teacher that I remember very well regarding the book of *fathul muin*. It sounds like this, "Whoever reads *fathul muin* fluently, God willing, he will easily understand jurisprudence from other books. Because the language of *fiqh* book is not much different. Because the language of *fathul muin* is difficult, while other books are not as difficult as *fathul muin*."

In addition, "anyone who studies the book of *fathul muin* but does not hold or refer to the book of *syarah*, namely the book of *i'alah ath-thalibin*, then he is arrogant. Understanding the *fathul muin* book is difficult if it is not accompanied by the *i'alah* book". Thus, it is still not appropriate when there are *santri* figures, researchers and jurists who claim to have a deep knowledge of religion when their understanding of jurisprudence in the book of *fathul muin* is not deep.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion of the article about the Book of *Fathul Muin* at the Tanurunida Islamic Boarding School can vary depending on the argumentation and purpose of writing. However, several possible conclusions that can be drawn from the article are: 1. The Book of *Fathul Muin* is one of the important *fiqh* books in Islamic heritage. This book discusses various aspects of Islamic law, such as worship, affairs, and family matters. 2. The authors of the book, such as Sheikh Zakaria Al-Ansari, used a directed approach and structured method, and referred to well-known and widely recognized sources of Islamic law. 3. The Book of *Fathul Muin* has a great influence on Islamic society. This book can be used as a reference by scholars and practitioners of Islamic law in understanding Islamic law and deciding legal issues. 4. Even though the Book of *Fathul Muin* has great influence, there are criticisms and questions about the opinions and interpretations described in this book. This criticism can be attributed to the suitability of opinions within the social and cultural context, as well as the expansion of the broader scope of Islamic law. In conclusion, the essay can provide an in-depth understanding of the contents of the *Fathul Muin* Book, the method of writing, and explanations of legal analysis, as well as influences and criticisms of this book. Conclusions can also provide the author's response to the problem, raise questions or directives for further research regarding a particular opening book.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

Further studies on the Implementation of Fathul Muin's Teaching Material Books to Improve Santri's Competence are urgently needed to increase students' understanding of the yellow book

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